

Historical Importance of Natural Heritage Monuments in Villupuram District, Tamil Nadu – A Study

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A B S T R A C T

This article focused to reveal the historical importance of natural heritage monuments in Villupuram district. Villupuram is the prominent centre which has unique history, from the pre-historic to modern era. Heritage is covered some of the edifices like structures, buildings, artifacts which precincts that aesthetic, cultural, architectural, and historic significance. Also it has natural features with unique environmental significance and precincts the scenic beauty such as sacred groves, hills, hillocks, water bodies (and the areas adjoining the same), open areas, wooded areas, etc. In the natural context, heritage includes mountains, landscapes, gardens, parks, wilderness, rivers, islands, flora, and fauna. The subjective human assessment dependent on the cultural components and its value depends on the history. The Natural heritage centres held in Villupuram district namely Gingee fort, Ennayiram, Thirunathar Kundru, and Kabilar Kundru. Villupuram was a unique to having almost all heritage monuments, especially natural. Because, this landscape is given the great possibility, to attribute the nature could be become heritage monuments.

Keywords: Natural Heritage Monuments, Protected Monuments, Ticketed Monuments, Edifices, Historical importance.

Introduction

Tamil Nadu has rich heritage monuments which depicted the culture and tradition. They are the witnesses of the life and livelihood of the people and rule of kings and queens. Though, the cultural heritage centres classified with its nature and position of the same. The important heritage monuments were protected by the central and State Government. The important act of protected monument is namely Tamil Nadu Ancient and Historical Monuments and Archaeological Sites and Remains Act, 1966. There are numerous heritage sites in Tamil Nadu both coastal and hinterlands have a unique cultural heritage, brought the name 'soul of the south'¹Heritage broadly means "something transferred from one generation to another." The word "heritage" includes both cultural and natural facets. In the cultural context, heritage describes both material and immaterial forms, e.g., artifacts, monuments, historical remains, buildings, architecture, philosophy, traditions, celebrations, historic events, and distinctive ways of life, literature, folklore, or education. In the natural context, heritage includes mountains, landscapes, gardens, parks, wilderness, rivers, islands, flora, and fauna. The subjective human assessment dependent on the cultural components and its value depends on the history. The word "heritage" is applied in a wide variety of contexts, and it is used as a synonym for objects from the past or for sites with no surviving physical structures but associated with past events. It could be enlarged with the past, artistic and cultural productivity. There are many countries has more heritage values has focused the culture of national identity.

Heritage is covered some of the edifices like structures, buildings, artifacts which precincts that aesthetic, cultural, architectural, and historic significance. Also it has natural features with unique environmental significance and precincts the scenic beauty such as sacred groves, hills, hillocks, water bodies (and the areas adjoining the same), open areas, wooded areas, etc. It could be classified that the landscape of cultural importance and significant heritage site which interpretation of the built heritage and through very high integral part, Heritage comprises archaeological sites, remains, ruins, and monuments protected by the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) and their counterparts in the United States and also a large number of unprotected buildings, groups of buildings, neighborhoods, and public spaces, including landscapes and natural features that provide character and distinctive identity to cities. Conservation plans and projects for cities must take into account both the protected and

unprotected components of their heritage. The three key concepts that need to be understood to determine whether a property is worthy of listing as a heritage property are, namely, historic significance, historic integrity, and historic context

Villupuram is the prominent centre which has unique history, from the pre-historic to modern era. It has lot of historical, cultural; heritage values depicted the archaic sources, and even the colonial documents. Before the bifurcation from Cuddalore, it was conjoined with Cuddalore district and named as South Arcot District. Now it has divided into two pieces namely Villupuram and Kallakurchi district. No doubt, Villupuram has all kind of heritage monuments from pre historic to Modern era. The Central Archaeological protected monuments, State archaeological protected monuments, ticketing monuments, are located in Villupuram district. Moreover, category wise natural, cultural and spiritual monuments are held in this region.

Natural heritage is the gift of nature which has been existed in the natural regions like mountains, deserts, forests, ocean etc.,² The Natural heritage centres held in Villupuram district namely Gingee fort, Ennayiram, Thirunathar Kundru, and Kabilar Kundru. Perhaps, the Villupuram region have the all kind of lands like *Kurinji*, *Mullai*, *Marudham*, *Neithal* and *palai* which mentioned in the Sangam literature, The nature blessed to the evolve the mankind for long years. So men are erected their habitual place in the hilly region very near to the river and natural shelters. These edifices have been acted as the greatest monuments protected by the Government in Tamil Nadu over the year. This article focused to reveal the natural heritage monuments in Villupuram district.

Gingee Fort

The Marathas fortified Gingee, later naming it "the most impregnable fort in India" and glorifying it as "the Troy of the East" by the British.³ Gingee Fort is otherwise known as *Jinji*, *Chenji*, and *Senchi*. Indeed, Gingee is the only surviving fort in Tami Nadu and Villupuram District. The small town of Gingee was once a capital city, with its province extending from Nellore in the north, according to local legend. Gingee Amman was one of the seven virgins who served as the village's guardian deities and was originally the site of a small fort built by the Chola dynasty during the 9th century A.D. Legend has it that around 1200 A.D., Gingee was

fortified by Ananda Kone, chief of the local shepherd community, in 1240 A.D. His successor, Krishna Kone, is said to have fortified the northern hill, which later fell to the Kurumbar, who established their headquarters at Sendamangalam, which later fell under the powerful Chola Empire. The beginning of recorded history may be found in the 16th century, when the Nayaka kings of Gingee (Gingee), who were subject to the growing Vijayanagar Empire, established their capital there. As the first of the Nayaka dynasty of Gingee rulers, Krishnadevaraya selected Krishnappa Nayaka, who is regarded as their founder.

During this time, the majority of the buildings, defensive walls, and temples were constructed. The fortifications and defenses were further strengthened under Chatrapathi Shivaji, the great Maratha ruler, who was captured in Gingee in 1677 A.D. Gingee came under the hegemony of the Moghul emperor Aurangzeb in 1691 A.D., and Sarup Singh was appointed as the chief of Gingee by the emperor, under the control of the Nawab Arcot. Sarup Singh's son, Raja De Singh, revolted against the Nawab of Arcot.

Fortification Walls

The massive fortification walls of Gingee interconnect the three inaccessible hills— Krishnagiri, Chandiragiri, and Rajagiri. The three hills are distributed in the form of a triangle, while the main wall connecting them is 20 metres thick. The inner fort is surrounded by numerous gates and walls, while the tops of the three hills constitute unassailable citadels. The Rajagiri citadel is the highest, at about 800 feet in height, and the most inaccessible. A bridge now spans the 20-meter-deep chasm.

Kalyana Mahal

Built in the Indo-Islamic style, the Kalyana Mahal of Vijayanagara is one of the most attractive ruins of the fort. It consists of a square courtyard surrounded by rooms for the women of the governor's household. In the center of this courtyard is a 27 meter high square tower built of stone. The tower has a pyramidal roof. This tower's interior spaces resemble other Vijayanagar Nayaka structures in other places. Venugopala Swamy Temple: Located to the west of the inner gate of the lower fort, the temple has a magnificent sculpture of Lord Krishna playing the flute

with his two companions. Another interesting feature of this temple is the finely polished wide smooth slab located in front of the temple.

Ponds

The road leading to the Hanuman Temple, located outside the lower fort, is dotted with temple ponds and many impressive structures. Chakkarakulam and Chettikulam are the two famous ponds of this fort. Chettikulam was built by Raja Shetty during the Maratha occupation of the place in the late 18th century. In the north of this pond is a platform believed to be the mound of Raja Desingh, where his young wife committed suicide. This fort is one of the most important tourist centers of the Villupuram region and presents the history, culture and traditions of the region from the Cholas to the present day.

Thirunathar Kundru

Thirunathar Kundru is about 2 kilometres away on the northern side of the Singhavaram route. This region is under the territory of Kadambur. Also, this place is glorified for its religion of Jainism. There is a route (a step) to take to reach this place. A hillock faced the east and had more than 24 sacred saints (Theerthangar) carved beautifully. Moreover, a saint's idol is located nearby on this hill. A mandapa held in this region has given details about the sacred saints (Jains) who occupied this place. There is a Tamil inscription (also known as Asokan Brahmi) near this location that reflects the origins of the Tamil alphabet as well as the glorification of this location. The hills are beautifully carved with Tamil letters (in large size). It also made reference to the transformation of Tamil letters from "*Tamili*" to "*Vatteluthu*" (scripted Tamil letters). Thirunathakundru denotes two words, namely "Thiru" and "Kundru." Thiru mentioned paying tribute to this region. "Kundru" means glorification of the hill, like Thiruparankundram. Nathar, the middle word, reflected the sacred saints of the Jain community. The hill consisted of two inscriptions.

Inscription pedagogy has

1. *Iympath thezhana*
2. *Santh Notra*

3. *Sandhira nandi*
4. *Sirigai nisitheegai*

Meaning

A teacher named Sandhira fasted for around 57 days until his death. The literary sources give details about the fast of the Jains. Above the inscriptions, it authenticates the fast of Jains that existed during the ancient period. Sandhira's teachings might be used as the teachings for the sacred saints in this region. There was no reference to the Tamil letter "AY," but this is the first reference to the "ay" letters given in this region. This inscription might belong to the period between the fourth and fifth centuries A.D. Moreover, Tamil letters are given a dot symbol in this place, which might have significance in this region. ⁴

The second one

1. *Muppathu nalasana Notra*
2. *Ilaya padarar nisithigai*

The young padarar, a Jain monk, fasted for thirty days, and another fasted for 57 days until death. ⁵ This also authenticates the practice of Jainism during the ancient period. ⁶

Kabilar Kundru (Kabilakkal)⁷

Thirukkivilur is situated on the bank of the South Pennar on the southern side. This place is located on the eastern side of Villupuram, the western side of Kallakurichi, Thiruvannamalai on the western side, and the southern side of Ulundurpet. Thirukkivilur's landscape stretches for approximately 2000 kilometers. The Malayan king had a capital in this region. This region was known in Sangam literature as "*Thunja Muzhuvir Koval*" and "*Muranmigu Kovalur*." Thirugnana Sambandar mentioned this place as "*Pothilvandu panseyiyum Poondan Kovalur*." Vaisnavism refers to Thirumangaiyalvar, Poigaiyalvar, and Poothathalvar, while other sources refer to this location as Koval. Cholas ruled this region from Thanjavur, having mentioned this place as "*Sri Maduranthaga Sathurvedu Mangalam*." The inscription depicted the name as "On" All the kings and feudatories glorified this palace and these hills. Thirumudikkari, the feudatories of the Chera,

Chola, and Pandya kings, ruled this region from 250 to 275 A.D. Purananuru is mentioned in Tamil literature as

'Kari Yurnthu Peramar kadantha

*Marigai marappor malayan*⁸

Kabilar, who arranged marriages with the king for Pari's⁹ daughters, was possibly the most important poet during the Sangam period.¹⁰ While the three dynasties, namely the Chera, Chozha, and Pandyas, held their supremacy over this land, the feudatories (seven patrons) emerged as the biggest kings in this land. Pari wanted to join Kabilar in his cabinet. He agreed to join his kingdom. For a long time, they have maintained friendships with one another. While three kings—Cheras, Choals, and Pandyas—made fruitful friendships with others, they then made an expedition over the Parambumalai, which was ruled by Pari. Kabilar met with the above-mentioned forces and asked to surrender, but they invaded their land and killed the king. Kabilar made amends by bringing Pari's daughters (Angavai and Sangavai) to Thirukkivilur, where he formed a matrimonial alliance with King Thirumudikkari's sons. Then he set fire to the hillock and died there, as mentioned in Rajendira's epigraphy from Thirukkivilur.¹¹ The hill was then given the name "Kabilakkal." This place has been controlled and protected by the Archaeological Survey of Tamil Nadu. There is a temple above the hillock that is patronized by Siva Lingas. This place is also known as "Idaichikal" by the locals. Now the name Kabilakkal was completely gone. Anirai Kavalan identified this place as a heritage monument and revealed the significance of this place.¹² Kabilar Kundru had been protected heritage monument from 1966 A.D under the act of 1966 of 25. Those who have involved in the activities of damaging this edifices and hills at once arrested and imprisoned by more than three months or 5000 rupees fine.¹³

Shatru Malleswaralayam Rock Cut Temple

The tradition of rock-cut temple architecture in India started during the time of Emperor Asoka (300 BC) in and around ancient Magadha and spread widely to the western part of the country later. But it took a long time to arrive in south India. Gingee Taluk, Villupuram, is home to the Sathru Malleswaram Dhalavanur Sathrumallan Rock Cut Temple. It is otherwise known as

"Vanpedu." Two Jain beds have been carved into the hillock, which is approximately 25 metres high. Only then would we know that the sacred Jain saints lived in this cave. The locals acted like the Panjapandavars (Mahabharatham) who lived in this cove and named it "panjapandavar malai" (Malai means "hill"). The king Mahendravarma Pallava carved this rock, like Vallam, Seeyamangalam and Trichy. Lord Siva was glorious in this place. ¹⁴

Epigraphs

This hill had three inscriptions: one in Sanctorn, another in the pillar, and another on the east side of the pillar. They padded one.

*Thandaratha Narenthena
Narendeanai Karitha
Sathrumallana Sailesmin
Sathrumalleshvaralaya.*¹⁵

The tradition of rock-cut temples architecture in India began during the ancient period Beans were placed around 5 feet from the bottom of the rock cut. There are three Mandapas (Mugu Mandapa, Artha Manadapa, and Sanctram) held in this rickety entrance hurling 3 feet steeply, around 5 steps.¹⁶ The Archaeological Survey of Tamil Nadu has looked after this rock cut. There are no pujas or festivals in this place.¹

Jambai Inscriptions Site

The Tamil-Brahmi script at Jambai has put all speculation to rest, as the epigraph reads: the abode given by "*Athiyan Neduman Anci, the Satyaputo.*" (See picture No. 3 on Plates). The Jambai inscription of Adiyaman Nedumanji must belong to the second century A.D. In that inscription, Adiyaman is referred to as Sathyaputo, and the title is spelled exactly the same way as in the second rock-cut inscription of Asoka at Girnar. The letter shape is similar to Asokan edicts but not to the well-known legend on Satakarni King's coin from the second century A.D. ¹⁸

To sum up, Villupuram was a unique to having almost all heritage monuments, especially natural. Because, this landscape is given the great possibility, to attribute the nature could be become heritage monuments. Indeed, the Jainism was flourished in this region for long years; the

saints were settled in the hillocks that made the settlement and their remissness become heritage in modern era. Also for the protection purpose, the fort was built namely Fort Gingee become the great existing fort impregnable nature, placed important role in the history of Villupuram. The only monument was ticketed monument in Villupuram district.

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